

CLEW BASED SCENARIOS FOR ACHIEVING NIGERIA NDC TARGETS

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Executive Summary

This study examines the effects of various power technology transitions on Nigeria's energy sector, employing the Climate, Land, Energy, and Water Systems (CLEWs) framework with the Open Source Energy Modelling System (OSeMOSYS). The analysis encompasses three scenarios: Baseline, 2070 NetZero, and Energy Transition Plan (ETP), to evaluate their impact on CO₂-equivalent emissions, land use, and water demand.

The Baseline scenario, which relies predominantly on coal and natural gas, results in high CO₂ emissions and significant water usage due to thermal power plants. It also maintains moderate land use, driven by fossil fuel infrastructure. The 2070 NetZero scenario shifts towards nuclear and renewable energy, leading to a reduction in emissions post-2045 while still requiring considerable water for nuclear power plants. This scenario also sees increased land use to accommodate carbon sinks. Conversely, the ETP scenario, featuring rapid adoption of renewables and natural gas as a transitional fuel, achieves net negative emissions by 2040 and significantly reduces water demand. However, it requires extensive land for deploying low-density renewable technologies.

The findings highlight the need for accelerated investment in renewable energy and enhancements in grid efficiency to support intermittent sources. Effective resource management is crucial to balancing energy demands with environmental impacts. Future research should focus on the electrification of the transportation sector and specific residential energy demands to further understand their implications. This integrated approach underscores the potential for renewables to align with Nigeria's climate objectives while fostering a sustainable and resilient energy system.

1. Introduction

Nigeria, Africa's most populous country and one of its largest economies, plays a pivotal role in the region's energy landscape. With a land area of approximately 923,768 square kilometres, Nigeria is richly endowed with natural resources, including vast oil and gas reserves, as well as significant potential for renewable energy sources such as solar and hydroelectric power. However, the country faces substantial challenges in its energy sector, marked by an energy mix that is heavily reliant on fossil fuels—particularly Natural gas, which account for over 70% of its energy production (IEA, 2023). Nigeria also has a high population growth rate, expected to hit 350 million people by mid-century and surpass the United States to become the third most populated country in the world.

Despite being a major energy producer, Nigeria suffers from a significant energy deficit, with nearly 85 million people lacking access to electricity, representing about 43% of its population (World Bank, 2022). The nation's electricity supply is notoriously unreliable, with frequent blackouts and a national grid that fails to meet the demand of its rapidly growing population and economy. This access challenge is exacerbated by the high cost of energy, inconsistent gas feed for power plants, underinvestment in

infrastructure, and the inefficiency of the existing power system. Environmental challenges further complicate Nigeria's energy landscape. Gas flaring and deforestation are major contributors to the country's greenhouse gas emissions. Gas flaring alone, a by-product of oil extraction, accounts for nearly 10% of the world's total gas flaring emissions (World Bank, 2022), while deforestation, driven by agricultural expansion to feed its rapidly growing population and fuelwood consumption, significantly impacts land use and carbon sequestration.

Given these challenges, there is an urgent need to explore how different energy technology transitions could impact Nigeria's emissions, land use, and water demand. This study evaluates the potential of adopting an integrated systems approach to energy planning, focusing on climate, land, energy, and water (CLEWs) interactions. The analysis considers three scenarios: The Baseline scenario, which continues the current reliance on fossil fuels; the 2070 NetZero scenario, which models Nigeria NDC policy target, and the Energy transition Plan (ETP) which envisions an aggressive transition to 100% renewable energy sources by 2040.

2. Methodology

In this research, the Climate, Land, Energy, and Water Systems (CLEWs) framework was utilized in conjunction with the Open Source Energy Modelling System (OSeMOSYS) tool. Although originally developed for energy systems analysis, OSeMOSYS's adaptability and flexibility allow for its application in integrated assessments of CLEWs. This integrated approach enables a comprehensive evaluation of the interactions and interdependencies among climate, land, energy, and water systems, supporting a holistic perspective in decision-making processes (Ramos et al., 2022). The Starter Data Kit (SDK) provided within the OSeMOSYS toolkit for Nigeria was employed as the baseline model, drawing on the reference energy system developed by Cannone and Allington (2021). Complementary data for agriculture and water sectors were sourced from reputable databases such as the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), and the International Energy Agency (IEA).

Three scenarios were constructed for this analysis as shown in Figure 1: Baseline, NDC, and ETP. The Baseline scenario represents the current state without any additional policy or resource constraints. The 2072 NetZero scenario introduces annual emission limits beginning in 2050, with a trajectory towards net-zero emissions by 2070, in alignment with Nigeria's Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs). The ETP scenario models Nigeria's Energy Transition Plan (ETP), as developed by Sustainable Energy for All (SE4ALL) in collaboration with the Nigerian Energy Transition Office and the Energy Transition Implementation Working Group. This scenario envisions accelerated investment in fast-deployable renewables such as solar and wind, with natural gas serving as a transition fuel until 2040. Post-2040, the

scenario anticipates a reduction in natural gas use, accompanied by increased investments in nuclear power, hydropower, and other renewable energy sources.

Figure 1: Scenarios for the CLEW's Model

The CLEWs (Climate, Land, Energy, and Water Systems) modeling methodology enabled a detailed analysis of technology-specific challenges and their implications for energy policy decision-making. While the overarching vision was integrated and considered various energy supply alternatives, the approach primarily focused on optimizing costs within the constraints of emissions and technology. The study did not seek to reassess challenges related to technological development, cost evolution, or the role of research and development. Instead, it concentrated on identifying areas where energy sector authorities could directly or collaboratively engage with other sectors to effectively advance the country's climate goals.

3. Results

This modeling exercise aimed to address the following research question: How can Nigeria's electricity deficit be addressed, and net-zero emissions be achieved through the application of integrated modeling frameworks within a least-cost optimization strategy?

The results provided insights into distinct trajectories across three scenarios: Baseline, 2070 NetZero, and ETP, each highlighting critical aspects of Nigeria's energy transition as shown in Figure 2:

- Baseline Scenario: There is a continuous and rapid deployment of coal power plants due to their low cost. Solar and wind technologies are introduced in the medium term, driven by anticipated cost reductions as renewable technology advances. In the long term, coal deployment persists alongside the development of Nigeria's geothermal capacity.

- 2070 NetZero Scenario: Coal and natural gas utilization is intensified until mid-century to fully utilize the remaining carbon budget. Beyond this period, there is a significant shift towards renewables, with nuclear power being employed as a baseload to meet the growing energy demand.
- ETP Scenario: Marked by an accelerated ramp-up of renewables, with natural gas acting as a transition fuel. This scenario sees substantial deployment of wind and rooftop solar to meet rising demand, and Nigeria's geothermal potential is expected to be fully realized by 2030. Nuclear energy becomes increasingly significant after mid-century. Solar and wind are particularly emphasized for their capacity to serve as mini-grids, effectively catering to sparsely populated rural areas.

Figure 2: Power Generation Capacity in the 3 scenarios

Figure 3 shows the analysis of CO₂-equivalent emissions across the three scenarios—Baseline, 2070 NetZero, and ETP—reveals distinct trajectories and implications for climate mitigation within the Land-Water-Energy Nexus:

Baseline Scenario: This scenario lacks any emissions constraints, leading to a significant rise in CO₂ emissions, which are projected to reach 780 million tonnes. This increase is primarily driven by the extensive use of coal and natural gas, reflecting a trajectory that is misaligned with global climate targets.

Net Zero Scenario: Initially, emissions follow a similar upward trajectory as in the Baseline Scenario, but a marked divergence occurs around 2045. At this point, the scenario prepares for rapid decarbonization to achieve net-zero emissions by 2070. This pathway represents a deliberate and strategic reduction in emissions, aligning with global efforts to mitigate climate change.

ETP Scenario: This scenario demonstrates the most aggressive approach to emissions reduction, achieving a net negative emission each year, with the lowest net emissions recorded in 2040 at -640,000 tonnes of CO₂. The ETP scenario achieves the lowest emissions rate among the three, aligning closely with Nigeria's climate

objectives and showcasing the transformative potential of renewable energy to drive substantial emissions reductions.

Figure 3: Total Emissions by Scenario

Exploring the performance of the three scenarios concerning carbon emissions, alongside an in-depth analysis of land and water dynamics, reveals crucial insights into balancing CO2-equivalent emissions mitigation with the optimisation of resource utilisation in the power sector. A particularly significant finding is the varied impact of agriculture and renewable energy sources on water and land demand, with biofuel production emerging as the most influential factor.

As illustrated in Figure 4, the Baseline scenario, which relies heavily on coal power, shows a substantial demand for water, primarily driven by the cooling requirements of thermal power plants. This scenario underscores the inherent trade-offs between fulfilling energy demands and minimising water consumption. The reliance on water-intensive power generation methods in this scenario highlights the challenges of sustainable resource management, where efforts to meet energy needs must be carefully balanced against the imperative to conserve vital water resources.

These dynamics illustrate the complexity of achieving a sustainable energy transition, where the integration of land, water, and energy considerations is essential for developing policies that are both environmentally and economically viable.

The 2070 NetZero scenario marks a significant shift toward nuclear and renewable power generation to align Nigeria's energy system with its Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs). Although this transition leads to a moderate reduction in water demand compared to the Baseline scenario, it still necessitates substantial water usage, particularly due to the cooling requirements of nuclear power plants. Conversely, the ETP scenario, which features an early and aggressive transition to renewable energy sources such as solar and wind, demonstrates a notable decrease

in water demand. This is largely attributed to the lower water intensity of renewables compared to both fossil fuels and nuclear power.

Figure 4: Water Usage across Scenarios

Land use dynamics were also examined across the three scenarios as shown in Figure 5. In the Baseline scenario, which relies predominantly on high-density fossil fuel power plants, the amount of land consumed for energy purposes is the lowest. This can be expected, as fossil fuels like coal and natural gas require less land per unit of energy produced compared to renewable sources. However, in the 2070 NetZero scenario, a sharp increase in forest land use occurs, driven by the need for extensive carbon sinks to offset emissions and achieve net-zero status by mid-century.

The ETP scenario, with its large-scale deployment of low-density renewable energy systems like wind and solar, uses the highest amount of land. Despite this increase, it is important to note that the overall land footprint of renewables remains relatively small. This finding challenges common misconceptions that large-scale renewable energy deployment necessitates extensive land use, underscoring the potential for renewables to be integrated into Nigeria's energy mix without causing significant disruptions to land availability.

Figure 5: Land cover across scenarios

4. Discussion

Nigeria's unique context plays a critical role in shaping its climate pathways, particularly when considering the availability and demand for land, water, and energy. These factors are instrumental in determining the cost-benefit dynamics of different climate strategies. The Nigerian energy sector is heavily reliant on fossil fuels, particularly natural gas, which is a significant contributor to the nation's energy mix and export revenues. Natural gas is poised to be a key transition fuel as Nigeria moves towards a more sustainable energy future.

The scenarios explored in this study highlight the potential for natural gas, particularly when paired with Carbon Capture, Utilization, and Storage (CCUS) technologies, to serve as a bridge towards lower carbon emissions. This approach not only leverages Nigeria's abundant natural gas resources but also mitigates the high land and water usage associated with coal and other fossil fuels. However, the adoption of renewable energy sources, such as solar and wind, is crucial for Nigeria's long-term climate goals. The ETP scenario, which emphasizes the rapid deployment of renewables, reveals the potential for significant reductions in water demand and carbon emissions. This scenario aligns closely with Nigeria's Nationally Determined Contributions (NDCs), underscoring the importance of integrating renewables into the energy mix. The CLEWs (Climate, Land, Energy, and Water Systems) approach offers valuable insights into how these technologies can be optimized to balance environmental impacts with energy production needs. While the Baseline scenario indicates a continued reliance on coal and natural gas, the shift towards renewable energy in the 2070 NetZero and ETP scenarios illustrates the potential for Nigeria to achieve its climate objectives. Notably, the ETP scenario suggests that renewable energy can play a pivotal role in reducing emissions, with solar and wind energy offering viable solutions for Nigeria's energy challenges, particularly in rural and off-grid areas.

One of the key findings of this analysis is the relatively low land requirement for renewable energy deployment in Nigeria, dispelling the common myth that large-scale solar and wind farms necessitate extensive land use. This is particularly important in Nigeria, where land use is a critical factor due to competing demands from agriculture and urbanization. The limitations of this modelling exercise must be acknowledged. The simplified CLEWs diagram used for Nigeria does not capture the full complexity of the nation's energy, land, and water systems.

Consequently, the insights provided offer a partial view of the potential outcomes of different climate pathways. Future research should aim to expand this model to include a broader range of technologies and scenarios, such as the integration of hydrogen and nuclear energy, as well as a more detailed analysis of the industrial and

transportation sectors. Further research could also explore the socio-economic implications of different energy transitions, particularly in terms of job creation, economic diversification, and energy access. Integrating these considerations with the technical analysis provided by the CLEWs framework would offer a more comprehensive understanding of the trade-offs and opportunities associated with Nigeria's energy transition.

5. Conclusion

This study has investigated the intricate relationships between power technology transitions and the interconnected systems of energy, land, and water in Nigeria. By examining three distinct scenarios—Baseline, 2070 NetZero, and ETP—this research has provided valuable insights into how integrated systems approaches can influence climate and resource management strategies. The study highlights that while renewable energy sources such as solar and wind offer considerable environmental benefits, their deployment requires a balanced approach to land use. The reduced land footprint for renewables compared to traditional fossil fuels dispels the notion that significant land areas are needed for large-scale energy projects.

For policymakers and stakeholders, the study recommends prioritizing investments in renewable energy technologies with lower environmental impacts and exploring innovative strategies to address the challenges of deforestation and greenhouse gas emissions. Nigeria's path to achieving its climate goals necessitates a nuanced understanding of the interplay between power technology transitions and the broader environmental context. Embracing integrated systems approaches will be crucial in navigating the complexities of energy, land, and water management, ultimately paving the way for a sustainable and equitable energy future.

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